

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF MEDICAL TERMINATION (AMENDMENT) ACT, 2021

by

Ananya Dutt
Assistant Professor
SRM University, Delhi NCR.

Introduction

Faye Wattleton had correctly pointed out, “Reproductive freedom is critical to whole range of issues. If we can’t take charge of this most personal aspect of our lives, we can’t take care of anything. It should not be seen as a privilege or a benefit, but a fundamental human right.”¹

Abortion seems to have strong polar effect on people all around the world. Abortion or termination of pregnancy can occur through two ways, either naturally as a miscarriage or can be brought deliberately, termed as induced abortion. It’s the latter part which causes uproar of controversy and especially in Indian context, such controversy dates back to ancient texts and manuscripts.

Recently, a leaked document which talked about the reversing the iconic judgement *Roe v. Wade*² which attempted to answer the question – ‘Does the US Constitution recognise a woman’s right to terminate her pregnancy by abortion?’, has sparked the debate once again regarding the acceptability of abortion in society.

What does Religion say about it?

In Hinduism, abortion or in hindi called as *Hatya*, as the name suggests, is seen a very negative light. According to hindu scriptures, the spirit or *atma* and matter or *prakriti* together forms life. As Caraka Samhita says, ‘the soul is already joined with the matter in the very act of conception’. In Satapatha Brahmana, the one aborting is compared to a sin similar to that of eating beef, while the Upanishads categories them with thieves and outcasts. In

¹ Prateek Mudgal, “Reproductive Choice of a Woman: A Fundamental Right”, Nithi Manthan Blog, <https://nitimanthan.in/blog-posts/blog-niti-manthan/2021/11/24/reproductive-choice-woman-fundamental-right/>, last visited on 2022, 1 May

² 410 U.S. 113 (1973)

Visnudharmasutra, killing of foetus or mother is equated with one of the worst crimes in Hindu religion³.

But on the other hand, Vishnu Purana narrated the pain the unborn foetus is in in his mother's womb and defines the consciousness in the womb as a soul or jantu possessing a subtle body or sukumaratanu tends to reside in womb or garba of the woman. The foetus stays there in folded position, tormented by the food his mother intakes and experiences severe pain, unable to stretch his limbs and floating around his own urine⁴. Also, The Garbha Upanishad states that ensoulment of soul takes place in seventh month of pregnancy. In Susruta Samhita, a medical text narrates the procedure to follow in case of complicated pregnancy with the ultimate objective to save both the parties – the mother and the child. It goes on to say that if in any case, a choice between the two has to be made, the life of mother takes precedence and thus an abortion is justified⁵.

Talking about the Islamic view on adoption, life is considered a gift that is bestowed upon the people which by its very nature is sacred and priceless. In chapter 5 verse 32, the Qur'an states that: "On that account: We ordained for the Children of Israel that if anyone slew a person unless it is for murder or for spreading mischief in the land it would be as if he slew the whole people: and if anyone saved a life it would be as if he saved the life of the whole people"⁶. Since Abortion is termination of life, hence it is considered immoral.

But if the ensoulment has not taken place yet, then abortion is not seen in bad light. Ibrahim B Syed, President of Islamic Research Foundation International brought forward four opinions of four different school of thought on when such ensoulment takes place. The Shafi School allows abortion upto 120 days from the date of conception. Hanafi School holds the view that abortion is permitted until the end of fourth month and the mother can take such step without requiring the consent of her husband if it is morally justified. Maliki School allows abortion upto 40 days but by consent of both parties and Hanbali School is of similar opinion⁷.

³ Lipner, Julius J. "On Abortion and the Moral Status of the Unborn", in *Hindu Ethics*, edited by Coward, Lipner, and Young. State University of New York, Albany. 1989.

⁴ Whitney, William Dwight, trns. *Atharva-Veda Samhita*. Harvard Oriental Series, vol. VII. Harvard University. Cambridge, MA. 1905.

⁵ Edward Omar Moad, Hindu Ethics on the Moral Question of Abortion, *Eubios Journal of Asian and International Bioethics*, 14 (2004), 149-59, University of Missouri, Columbia

⁶K. Aramesh., Abortion: An Islamic Ethical View. *Iran J Allergy Asthma Immunol.*, 6 (2007), pp. 29-33

⁷ Mohamad Firdaus Mohamad Ismail, Abdurezak Abdullahi Hashi^b, Mohd Said bin Nurumal^a, Muhammad Lokman bin Md Isa, *Islamic Moral Judgement on Abortion and its nursing application: an expository analysis*,

Judaism also supports abortion in cases where it is necessary to save mother's life. The Mishnah states that where there exists danger to mother's life, then in those cases an abortion can be performed at any stage from conception until the head of infant emerges.⁸

Different practices bring different ideas of what is and what is not okay to do when it comes to a mother's choice to keep or not to keep the body. Apart from these many directions, there is also State that through its barbaric laws dictate what is correct procedure to be followed by a mother.

The Legal Aspect

The Right to life is a well-established fundamental right embodied under Article 21 of our Indian Constitution. Amongst all rights provided to women, Right to Abortion which forms the part of Right to Privacy has been in spotlight for quite some time. But the question that arises is that whether an unborn foetus should be treated as a human being?

The first legislation in India that governed Right to Abortion was Indian Penal Code, 1860 which deals with criminal law of the country. Section 312 to 316 criminalised abortion. Though nowhere it mentions the term 'Abortion' but rather mentions the term 'miscarry' and 'unborn child', however with help of legal precedents and interpretations we came to know that miscarriage means causing criminal abortion.⁹

After the Shantilal Shah Committee¹⁰, the need to realise the regulation of Abortions in view of more flexible law in India and hence on 10 August 1971, the Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act came into existence. Unfortunately, the committee stated in its report "that legalising medical termination of pregnancy with a perspective on acquiring segment results is strange and may even lose the useful and positive act of family arranging through contraception"¹¹

The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971 was enacted by legislature to provide mechanism for termination of 'certain pregnancies' by registered medical practitioners. The

Ist International Nursing Scholars Congress, Indonesia, 212-216Kulliyah of Nursing, International Islamic University of Malaysia, Pahang, Malaysia (2018)

⁸ Bleich, J. David. "ABORTION IN HALAKHIC LITERATURE." *Tradition: A Journal of Orthodox Jewish Thought*, vol. 10, no. 2, 1968, pp. 72–120. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23256253>. Accessed 29 May 2022.

⁹ Upendra Baxi, Abortion laws in India, *Journal of Indian Law Institute*, 1986-87, Vol-28-29.

¹⁰ Shri Shantilal H. Shah, "Report of The Committee to Study the Question of Legalization of Abortion, 1967", 51-53 (1967).

¹¹ Government of India, Report of committee to study the question of legislation of abortion, 1966.

preamble of the Act states that “This is an Act to provide for termination of pregnancy by registered medical practitioner for matters associated therewith or incidental thereto.”¹² The Act, in its 51 years of existence has been amended twice, in 2002 and 2021. Though medical science has made tremendous advancement not only in technology but also sophisticated techniques but unfortunately, the most recent amendment fails to reflect the same.

Under the Medical Termination of Pregnancy (Amendment) Act, 2021, some progressive changes were made taking in account the 194 writ petitions filed before Supreme Court of India and various High Courts between June 2016 and April 2019 by women seeking to medically terminate their pregnancy wherein, they identified several systematic issues that resulted in varied and inconsistent outcomes.¹³

The Principal Act under section 3 stated that authorization of two medical practitioners is required for termination of pregnancy for gestational period of twelve to twenty-three weeks. The Amendment led to increase of Gestation limit to twenty-four weeks only on a pre-condition like when in opinion of two medical practitioners, such pregnancy causes risk to life and physical or mental health of woman or child; or it is because of result of failure of measures taken by woman or her partner to prevent pregnancy; caused by rape

In *X v. Govt. of NCT of Delhi*¹⁴, a 18 weeks pregnant HIV positive woman filed petition in Delhi High Court against the denial of concerned authorities to terminate her pregnancy. She had attained such condition as a result of forced prostitution. The High Court allowed the termination of her pregnancy, relying on Section 3 of the MTP Act, and in particular her willingness to terminate a pregnancy that resulted from rape as well as the mental, physical, social and economic problems that the woman was likely to face from continuation of the pregnancy

In High Court on its own motion *v. State of Maharashtra*, Bombay High Court stated that any such undesirable pregnancy that goes on to represent a violation of the woman's bodily integrity and aggravates her mental trauma which would be deleterious to her mental health.”

A shift in scenario occurs when judgements which does not favour the woman in question rights and rather prefers to go with the opinion of Medical Board.

¹² The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971, No. 34, Acts of Parliament 1971 (India).

¹³ Debanoana Choudhari, '50 years on, India's Abortion Law Still Has Serious Gaps', Sept, 29, 2021, <https://thediplomat.com/2021/09/50-years-on-indias-abortion-law-still-has-serious-gaps/>

¹⁴ 2013 SCC OnLine Del 6473.

Like in *R and another V. State of Haryana*¹⁵, a girl who had gotten pregnant because of the torturous act of Rape was denied to abort the child by doctors. By the time Court heard her case, she was 22 weeks pregnant wherein the court set up a medical board which further opined that such pregnancy would cause no harm to the girl. With direction to state government to provide her with Rs. 5000/- per month and lumpsum amount of Rs. 5,00,000/- in her account, Court denied the termination of pregnancy.

Similarly, Supreme Court in *Savita Patil v. Union of India*¹⁶, denied the right to terminate the pregnancy of 26 weeks pregnant woman when Medical Board made it clear that there was no physical and mental injury to the woman.

The “Medical Board” has been defined under Section 2 (i)(aa) of the (Amendment) Act, 2020 and it provides that medical board has to be constituted in every state and union territory and it shall be composed of a gynaecologist, radiologist and the other members which the state government shall notify.

Section 5A of the said Act provides that a registered medical practitioner can only disclose the information of any abortion to only a person authorised by law and to no other person. In the contravention of the said rules, the person shall be punished with an imprisonment which may extend to one year or with fine or both.

Where the Problem lies

The Act with its latest amendment pays no heed to Right of Privacy and Constitutional Right to make reproductive choices, along with Body Autonomy of the pregnant woman. Only under compelling circumstances like that of ‘grave injury to mental and physical health’ and other mentioned before is when the woman may be permitted to terminate her pregnancy. Such set norms renders motherhood the norm and abortion the exception. And as cherry to the unappetising cake, her consent in such compelling circumstances is insufficient without a validation from medical practitioner.

The Amendment permits the termination in case ‘the child were born it would suffer from any serious physical or mental abnormality’ but Section 3(2B) makes the upper gestational limit inapplicable if in opinion of Medical Board there isn’t any ‘substantial foetal abnormality’. The

¹⁵ CWP 6733 of 2016

¹⁶ (2017) 13 SCC 436.

Amendment also does not specify the categories of woman who may terminate pregnancies between 20-24 weeks and leaves it to be prescribed through Rules.

Though, it is appreciable for being progressive and liberal as under Section 3(2) the terms ‘married woman’ and ‘her husband’ is replaced with “any woman’ and ‘her partner’. But with Transgender Persons (Protections and Rights) Act, 2019 recognises transgender as third gender, it has no mention in the Medical Termination Act.

Conclusion

It is paramount to know the motive behind the abortion laws. The primary motive and idea behind its enactment is to provide the woman a better feasibility service for terminating the pregnancy. In India, after passing of the Medical termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971 it did not solve all the hurdles and problems but it afforded an opportunity for the women who were earlier not allowed to terminate the pregnancy except on the ground that the life of the pregnant woman is at risk. Now, in present time after passing of Medical termination of Pregnancy (Amendment), Act 2020 many of loopholes of the prior Act were ratified and much attention were given to the unmarried women, and rape victims.

While looking at national laws of other countries, like in the UK, a pregnancy may be terminated at any time: (i) to protect the life of the woman, (ii) to prevent grave permanent injury to the physical or mental health of the woman, or (iii) if the child is at risk of being seriously handicapped. Further, when determining the injury to the woman’s physical or mental health, her actual or reasonably foreseeable environment may be considered¹⁷.

In South Africa, a pregnancy may be terminated up to 12 weeks at the request of the woman, and between 12 to 20 weeks if: (i) it poses a risk to the mental or physical health of the woman, (ii) there is a risk of foetal abnormalities, (iii) it was caused due to rape, or (iv) continuing the pregnancy would affect the socio-economic circumstances of the woman. It is also permitted beyond 20 weeks if there is a risk to the life of the woman or the foetus, or if there is a risk of foetal abnormalities.¹⁸

¹⁷ Section 1, Abortion Act 1967, <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1967/87/section/1>.

¹⁸ Choice on Termination Pregnancy Act, 1996, South Africa, https://www.parliament.gov.za/storage/app/media/ProjectsAndEvents/womens_month_2015/docs/Act92of1996.pdf.

Legislature should consider the giving full autonomy to the woman who has freedom to practice all rights guaranteed to her under Constitution of India. The Amendment is indeed a positive step towards the future of Right of Abortion in India but it has long way to go to be perfect in its place.

Indian Journal of Contemporary
Legal and Social Issues